

×*Hanshansenara*, a New Nothogenus in Agavaceae

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Abstract—The new nothogenus ×*Hanshansenara* is proposed.

×*Hanshansenara* M.H.J.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.** = *Agave* L. × *Manfreda* Salisb. × *Polianthes* L. = ×*Hansara* Avent ex J.Spath & J.Moore (in *Agaves* [Spath & Moore] 36. 2021), nom. illeg., non ×*Hansara* M.H.J.van der Meer (in *Cact. Phantast.* 2019(3)-2: 15. 2019). Etymology: Named for Hans Hansen, who developed the hybrid.

